

‘Domestic Violence’ – Problems, Perspectives and Solutions

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ABSTRACT

Violence and unrest is the order of the day, be it in the street, society or at national level at the present time. We can understand it from the perspective that may be because of greed or for power or for selfish ends. Surprisingly, if we look at individuals, everybody wants to be happy, joyful and enjoy their life to core. Of course, personal interests vary in the area they are interested to enjoy. One thing is clear that everybody wants to be joyful and they want to spend fruitful time with their family and friends. The last thing that anybody expects is violence ‘at home’ and Women is the victim in majority of the cases with an exception here and there. The statistics surprises one and all that domestic violence is on the rise across the world and not just particularly in one nation or one society or among the poor or weaker sections of the society but across the world in the houses where finances are not the basic requirement of the family at all. This paper presents the activity conducted in ‘Gender Sensitization Lab’, a newly introduced course by JNTUH, making use of prescribed Textbook “Towards World of Equals” along with video clippings from the youtube with outcomes of discussions and deliberations, influences of the fellow student opinions resulting to a sea change in the thinking of budding engineers and understanding the causes and finding solutions to the domestic violence.

Key words: Violence, family, society, and gender sensitization.

Introduction

Majority of the people in the society have become insensitive to the basic disturbances either at home or in the society. This is because of the presence of unrest at every level of the society irrespective of their social backdrop or financial status. Once the disturbance or unrest intensifies, it turns out to be violence. Unfortunately, violence has become omnipresent and peaking out at home resulting to Domestic violence. Woman is the victim in majority of the cases with an exception here and there. Therefore, there is an immediate need to attend this problem before it turns out to be gigantic and incurable. The Gender Sensitization Lab and the activities conducted in the session helped the faculty to work for the following:

Objectives of the paper

1. To identify the main causes of the problem
2. To understand the causes and their relevance to the present Society
3. To discuss the possible solutions and
4. To find the ways and means to avoid such situations and to bring harmony in the family

Introductory talk and Video Presentations

In order to make the students think on the topic ‘Domestic Violence’ and to meet the objectives mentioned above, the faculty gave a small introductory talk on ‘Domestic Violence’ before presenting the video of Leslie Morgan Steiner with the title of the TED talk ‘why domestic violence victims don’t leave’ downloaded from Youtube from the web link <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=INJjEZoRKqM> where Leslie shared secrets of domestic violence from the incidents of her personal life with various stages of violence and the probable solutions to the problems and how she could come out of the problems published on youtube on 4 December, 2012. The talk was for # 16 minutes. The Leslie presentation in brief is as follows:

Leslie Morgan Steiner graduated from Harvard College in B.A, MBA from Modern Business School and moved to New York City for the first job as writer and editor for a magazine and spent most of her career working for fortune 500 companies like Johnson & Johnson. Her first message was ‘Domestic violence happens to everyone, all races, all religion, all income and education levels, its everywhere’. Her second message was everyone thinks that domestic violence happens to women alone and it’s a women’s issue. In United States women of 16 to 24

ages are more subjected to domestic violence and about 85% of domestic violence victims are women. Over 500 women are killed every year by the abusive boyfriends or husbands.

She knows nothing about this when she met the Corner for the first time on a cold stormy January night. They started chatting, interacting on regular basis with one another, slowly and steadily Corner adored and amazed her by showing lot of interest in the details of her education, job and all other activities that she does with his intriguing enthusiasm and charming looks, fun and loving chat sharing his childhood secrets, the 'first stage' of seducing the victim, she opines. The 'second stage' was to isolate the victim with physical, financial and psychological trap. He trapped her into second stage by quitting his dream job stating that there is no need for him to prove his success in life to anyone and anymore and wants to live by her side in a tiny island of New England. It was a 'big sacrifice' she felt and quit her dream job and left New York City. The 'third stage' is to threaten the victim. He did the same to her by purchasing three guns stating that he needed to feel safe. He married her and at least twice a week he subjected her to severe physical and psychological violence. As she quit her dream job in New York, she was already trapped financially. She says, one in three, every American woman experiences the domestic violence and stocking at some point in her life, the Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) reports that 15 million children are abused every year. But unfortunately, everyone thinks that they alone suffer like this and does not share with anyone. But she started sharing her problems with friends, neighbours, police and everybody and hence she could get out of this problem, rescued and married again and blessed with three children and leading a happy life for the last 20 years. She says for sure 'she might have been killed', if she remains silent and receives all the abuse. At the end, she says, the most positive and doing well solution to end domestic violence is raise your voice share it with everyone you know else there is every possibility to get killed, if you silently receive abuse.

Discussions and Video Presentation

Immediately after the presentation of video, the faculty recapped the important points shared by Leslie by assisting the students who attentively listened and proactively shared with the class. After the small interaction of faculty-students, students-students, another TED talk video by Deepika Bhardwaj on domestic violence with a title "Men - The forgotten gender" made at IIFT Delhi, published on youtube on 26 Feb, 2015. The video talk was for # 19 minutes and

downloaded from the web link https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1_2gl7lz25E. The presentation of Deepika in brief is as follows:

She started her speech sharing her opinion that like any other women, she also felt that men does not have any issues and cannot be the victims of domestic violence. She is an advocate by profession and was shocked to witness the typical case of divorce where the lady with extra marital affair accused the husband (Deepika's close relative) and in-laws under dowry case and domestic violence supported by the sister of the lady stating that all the laws are in favour of women, whereas, the fact was that husband was innocent and moved by her unfair and illicit affairs, coupled with accusations of dowry and domestic violence cases killed himself. This was the turning point to the mindset and thinking of Deepika Bhardwaj. She was also stirred up by the video left by Maqdoom another male victim of domestic violence laws who committed suicide. She moved into tears and could not remain silent and took the project of preparing a documentary with the title 'martyrs of marriage' which presents the story of men who fought, and the men who are victims for the cruel acts of women leading to suicide or divorce. She further presents the statistics of most abused Indian Penal Code (IPC) 498A section, a law which was prepared and enacted with the noble intensions to prevent and protect the married women turned to be the unfair means to women to subject the husband and in-laws. She says only 15% were convicted against the cases booked under this section shows how much this law was abused by women. Furthermore, she presents the statement made by the Supreme Court in a case, where the apex court categorically accepted the fact that this was law excessively misused. Yet the law was not amended even when many committees and authorities recommended for changes. She also presented her findings on the other side of the Rothak Brave hearts case where Mr.Kuldeep lost the opportunity to join armed forces. She also shared the statistics reported by Women Commission on the rape cases filed during the April 2013 to July 2014, a whopping 53% were false. She also presented the thorough research made by 'The Hindu', a reputed and daily news paper, on the rape cases filed in New Delhi also termed as 'Rape capital of India', 40% of the cases include the fact that the girls willingly eloped with boys and the cases were filed by parents of the girl when they returned, 25% are consensual relationships turned out sour and termed as rape. The acquittal rate has gone from 46% to 70% out of the rape cases booked after the 'Nirbhaya' case. Media never reports the acquittals for the fear of lower TRP rating and the society believes that men do not have any problems or issues. The statistics also show that the

suicides by married men are twice that of women. The Gender laws across the world are equal to both men and women whereas in India it is only supporting women and there are no commissions to safeguard the interest and rights of men or their issues. A volunteer organization not supported by the government titled as 'Save Indian family' gets 135 calls every day from distressed men sharing their problems and issues. The current cases pending in the judiciary are around 3 crore. The need of the hour is Gender neutral laws, the victim should be protected, and culprit should be punished. Finally, she justified her stance for supporting the victim and not the oppressor.

Discussions

After going through the presentations of both Leslie and Deepika, the faculty taken up the discussion on the points made and the causes for 'Domestic Violence' with the help of the prescribed text book 'Towards World of Equals' by Susie Tharu and others. Students read out the contents of the topic and shared their opinion on the issues of the topic in the book 'Is home a safe place', rebuilding lives, new formula for justice, and when women unite (film).

Group Activity

Students were given 15 minutes of time to discuss with peer group, reflect on their ideas, thoughts and to pen them on paper to further share and interact with all other classmates.

Outcome of the deliberations

The following are some of the points shared by students which helped them to discuss furthermore and ponder a little more on their thoughts with regard to the issue:

- 1) Financial and social backdrop of the person may cause irrational behaviour
- 2) Majority of the cases illogical and petty issues leading to bad behaviour and critical situations in domestic life
- 3) Lack of discerning attitude of men and women
- 4) Carried away by the comparisons of materialistic possessions
- 5) Illogical and undesirable Greed leading to domestic violence
- 6) Easy attitude on the marital oaths taken
- 7) The forgotten objectives of married life

Conclusion

This paper began with the brief presentation of the faculty on the topic ‘domestic violence’ at the present juncture with an objective to identify the main causes, understand the relevance to the present society, to find out probable solutions and to bring about the ways and means to avoid such situations in domestic life so that there is harmonious family life leading to the ultimate objectives of married life. The video presentation of Leslie Morgan Steiner helped students to understand the fundamental causes of domestic violence followed by the discussions made them to relate the same to the present society. The video presentation of Deepika Bhardwaj helped students to think neutrally without taking sides, to find out a solution where we can have the society with happy families. The discussions among the peer group followed by presentations of the students led to motivation of fellow students towards harmonious life, fruitful interaction paved way to wonderful thoughts and opinions shared by the students on the benefits of happy family, how a family can have ‘LOVE and LIVE LIFE’ without the traces of domestic violence. The Gender Sensitization Lab helped students to share their heart in the language they are comfortable yielding positive results in motivating youth to speak out openly to form an idealistic society with happy families.

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